

IMPACT OF A PROJECT DEVELOPMENT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY IN THE ECONOMICS COURSE OF THE BACHELOR DEGREE IN BUILDING ENGINEERING

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Abstract

The development of practical activities in the classroom is essential for applying and deepening theoretical knowledge and for fostering profound learning by integrating theory and practice. This case study investigates the impact of a practical project on the academic performance of 596 Building Engineering undergraduate students enrolled at Universitat Politècnica de València, in the course on Economics. Participants were divided into an experimental group and a control group (who carried out an academic project on entrepreneurship in the course / who did not). Academic performance was assessed based on the final outcome in the course (pass/fail) and the result in the entrepreneurship content of the second midterm exam (pass/fail). Academic data were analyzed using the non-parametric Chi-square test. The results showed that students who completed the project passed the subject and the theoretical assessment of "entrepreneurship" content more frequently. This study concludes that implementing practical academic projects significantly enhances students' performance and achievement, highlighting the importance of these pedagogical methodologies in higher education.

Keywords: Academic performance, Academic project, Higher education, Theoretical and practical teaching.

1 INTRODUCTION

The learning process and assessment in education have been widely studied, both internationally [1, 2] and in Spain [3], with the aim of identifying the factors that influence students' academic performance. Among such factors, various pedagogical methodologies have been explored, such as the flipped classroom and service-learning [4 - 6]. Furthermore, attention has been paid to the physical design of the educational environment. Thus, it has been shown that the appropriate design of the learning space can have a significant influence on students' attention and memory performance [7]. However, besides these factors, classroom activities play a crucial role. One of these activities is practical coursework, which not only complements formal teaching, but also provides additional opportunities to apply and deepen acquired knowledge [8]. This way, by making students integrate theory and practice, both practical activities and coursework are intended to foster deep learning.

Assigning coursework is one of the educational strategies employed by teachers, often considered valuable in reinforcing learning and improving students' final grades. Previous research suggests that the development of educational projects contributes significantly to academic achievement when they are effectively designed and aligned with learning objectives [9]. Other authors have further explored the mediating variable that could be influencing this work-final grade relationship. Thus, it has been shown that the completion of academic tasks can improve understanding of the contents and promote self-management and responsibility skills [10]. In addition, continuous assessment through coursework allows students to receive formative feedback, which can help them identify improvement areas before final exams [11] and can act as another mediator of the relationship. This feedback is crucial, as it facilitates a learning cycle where students can adjust their study approaches and improve their performance over time [12]. Student motivation also plays an essential role in making coursework more effective. According to Ryan and Deci [13], intrinsic motivation, which refers to engagement in an activity because of inherent interest and enjoyment, can be significantly enhanced when students perceive that the assigned tasks are relevant and useful to their learning. Coursework can serve as a tool to increase this motivation by providing students with greater autonomy and a sense of purpose in their learning.

These studies have historically focused on primary [14, 5] or secondary education [15]. Although they have also been extended to other educational contexts such as higher education. Thus, the implementation of active and practical methodologies that encourage the real application of acquired knowledge has become a growing trend in higher education. Indeed, traditional teaching based on lectures and theoretical exams has been widely criticised for its limited capacity to develop practical

skills and transversal competences [16], lacking the benefits of active learning [17]. In response to these criticisms, a variety of student-centred educational approaches have been proposed that encourage active participation and learning based on the application of theoretical content to project development. These approaches not only improve academic performance, but also develop critical skills such as teamwork, effective communication, problem solving and critical thinking.

The purpose of this study is to analyse the impact of this practical methodology on the academic performance of the students enrolled in the Economics course of the Bachelor Degree in Building Engineering at Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV). To this end, the academic results obtained in the course by the students who participated in the project are compared with those who did not. The aim is to determine whether the implementation of an academic project contributes to improving students' passing rates and final grades.

We begin by presenting a short description of the Economics course under study, to give the reader some context. The discussion then turns to our method of investigation which took a quantitative approach. Then results are included and we end with the discussion and conclusions.

2 CONTEXT: ECONOMICS COURSE

This research focuses on the Economics course of the Bachelor Degree in Building Engineering, taught at the School of Building Engineering (ETSIE) of the UPV. The course has evolved over the years as a consequence of the adaptation to the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). Details about its evolution can be found elsewhere [18-20]. At present "Economics" is placed in the first year and first semester of the degree, and it has a load of 7.5 ECTS credits (European Credit Transfer System), which implies a total of 202.5 hours (75 classroom hours and 127.5 hours of students' independent work).

The course is divided into two main parts: General Economics and Business Management in the construction industry [21]. The first one provides students with a basic understanding of the current economic environment, covering both microeconomics and macroeconomics, with a special focus in the construction industry and the real estate market. As regards the second part, it includes finance topics and accounting interpretation, as essential for business financial management. In addition, content on business creation and business model idea generation is taught. For this purpose, knowledge from the previous parts is applied and basic knowledge for business creation is included such as forms of business ownership, organizational structures and charts, decisions related to marketing and economic feasibility.

The 75 hours of classroom teaching are organized in 30 sessions of 2.5 hours each, of which the first 12 sessions are assigned to teach part 1 content and 18 sessions for the second part (see Table 1).

These contents are taught by combining theoretical lectures with the resolution of practical exercises in the classroom, both individually and in teams. Thus, no session consists entirely of a traditional lecture. In addition, during the sessions assigned to the topic of business creation and entrepreneurship, students can voluntarily develop an academic project in teams of 4 to 6 members. The project consists of the development of a business plan for a business idea where to apply the knowledge acquired during the course, with the tutoring of the teacher. The business plan must be delivered in a poster format A1 (see Fig. 1) and has to be defended face to face in the last 2 final sessions of the semester.

The course assessment consists of two mid-term exams, one for each part, with a 40% weight each. The business creation content of the second mid-term exam is assessed by means of a multiple-choice test comprising 16 questions with 4 options, only one of them correct. Correct answers add up, errors subtract, while unanswered questions neither add nor subtract. This is intended to minimize students' random response.

The average of the two mid-term exams accounts for 80% of the final course grade, while 20% corresponds to the assessment of the academic project on entrepreneurship. All percentages are summative, with no minimum grade required.

Table 1. Basic structure of the Economics course.

	Session	Contents	Methodology*
Part I	1-6	Microeconomics	■
	7-12	Macroeconomics	■
Part II	13-18	Accounting	■
	19 - 22	Sources of finance	■
	23	Business idea and business plan development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity • Entrepreneurial ecosystems • Idea generation techniques (brainstorming, focus groups ...) and business idea development 	■ + ■
	24	Business Model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for its development such as Lean Canvas o Business Model Canvas 	■ + ■
	25	Management plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forms of business ownership • Organizational structures (charts) • Human resource management 	■ + ■
	26	Market analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Macro environment analysis (PEST/PESTEL analysis) • Micro environment analysis (Products, customers, competitors and suppliers) • Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) 	■ + ■
	27	Marketing plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing MIX (product, price, promotion and distribution) • Competitor and buyer mapping 	■ + ■
	28	Economic plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cash Budget, balance sheet, profit and loss account and financing possibilities 	■ + ■
	29 y 30	Final result	Oral Presentation

*The green color refers to practical and theoretical activities 100-minute long developed during the sessions. The orange color refers to the application of the content to the academic project and teacher's tutoring, corresponding to the last 50 minutes of each session.

3 METHODOLOGY

The case study presented here was developed during 2022/23 and 2023/24 academic years. It focuses on the part on business creation and entrepreneurship and students' elaboration of the poster. This academic project not only seeks to reinforce the theoretical concepts learned in the classroom, but also to provide students with hands-on experience of how to apply them in a real business environment. During each course, academic data was collected from the students and then analyzed.

Figure 1. Poster examples.

3.1 Participants

This research was carried out with the 596 students enrolled in the “Economics” course during the 2022/23 and 2023/24 academic years.

These participants were divided into two groups: those who carried out the academic project (experimental group) and those who did not (control group). The criteria for inclusion in each group depended on participants themselves, since the project was developed on a voluntary basis during classroom sessions.

Table 2 shows the general characteristics of the participants in terms of type of enrolment (regular and special, including those derived from mobility or degree homologation programs), sex (male and female) and academic year (2022/23 and 2023/24). Note that students enrolled in 2022/23 represent 39,9% of the sample and those enrolled in 2023-24 account for 60,1%. In terms of sex distribution, 50,7% of all participants were male and 49,3 were women.

Table 2. Participants' characteristics (age: $\bar{x} = 19,56$ years old; $\sigma = 1,01$).

			Control group	Experimental group
Regular enrolment	Female	2022/23	12	93
		2023/24	28	157
	Male	2022/23	19	111
		2023/24	37	134
Special enrolment	Female	2022/23	1	1
		2023/24	0	2
	Male	2022/23	0	1
		2023/24	0	0

3.2 Variables under study

Three main variables have been considered for the analysis: completion and delivery of the academic project, students' final grade for the course and achievement or performance in the "business creation" part.

- Academic project: This is a qualitative variable of a dichotomic nature (yes/no project completion). The condition of "experimental group" was assigned and determined in the final project oral presentation to all the students who had carried out the team classroom work during the 6 sessions assigned for this purpose. On the other hand, the rest of the students who did not attend the final oral presentation and, therefore, did not carry out the project, were assigned to the "control group" condition.
- Final course result (Course-Result): This is a qualitative dichotomic variable (pass/fail), obtained from the sum of the average grades of the mid-term exams, multiplied by 0.8, and the grade of the voluntary academic project multiplied by 0.2. The highest possible score was 10 points. Hence, if the course result was lower than 5 points the student confronted the situation of failure, while if the final grade was equal or higher than 5 the situation was a pass.
- Performance in Business Creation (Performance-BC): Qualitative dichotomic variable (pass/fail), obtained from the specific section on "business creation" included in the second mid-term exam, assessed with 2 points out of 10. Therefore, if the student obtained a score of less than 1 in this section, he/she had the situation of failure, while if the final grade was equal to or higher than 1, the situation was a pass.

To do this, the score in the section was first calculated as the sum of the correct multiple-choice questions answered correctly (0.125 points for each question) minus the incorrect multiple-choice questions (0.0417 points for each question) of the total of 16 questions.

3.3 Data analysis

SPSS v27 software was used to analyze the data. Since the normality test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) showed a p-value < 0.001, it was determined that the data did not follow a normal distribution. Therefore, the non-parametric Chi-square statistical test was used.

This test is used to evaluate the association of the Academic Project completion variable with the variables of Performance in Business Creation and the Final course result. This test makes it possible to determine the existence or not of a significant relationship between the completion of the project and the pass/fail rates both in the course and in the specific "business creation" assessment.

4 RESULTS

Firstly, a Chi-square analysis was performed to examine the relationship between the completion of class work and the final result of the course (pass/fail). Contingency Table 3 shows that the majority of students who carried out the classroom work passed the subject (335 out of 499), while the majority of those who did not failed (94 out of 97).

The Chi-square test indicates that this relationship is significant ($\chi^2(1) = 135.677, p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong association between coursework completion and the final course result. However, since the final course result depended on the grade obtained in the voluntary academic project (2 points out of the total) to some extent, a more specific Chi-square analysis was performed. Thus, the relationship between developing the project or not developing was also significant with performance in "business creation" ($\chi^2(1) = 332.611, p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Distribution of pass-fail rates between experimental and control groups.

	Course-Result		Performance-BC	
	Pass	Fail	Pass	Fail
Control group	3	94	3	94
Experimental group	335	164	181	318
Total	338	258	184	412

Fig. 2 represents an analysis of these results based on whether the project was undertaken by students. It shows that those who participated in the project had a higher pass rate in the course. The proportion of students who passed in the experimental group was 67.74%, while in the control group it was 3.09%. Similarly, there was a higher percentage of students who passed in the group that carried out the project compared to those who did not (36.27% vs. 3.09%). In addition, most of the students who did not carry out the project failed both in the course result and in business creation performance.

Figure 2. Proportions of the combinations of the categories of the variables studied.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This case study carried out in a higher educational context addresses the benefits of developing an academic project in order to improve students' learning processes. The implementation of this approach in the "Economics" course at ETSIE-UPV has shown a positive impact on students' academic performance. Those who participated in the project performed better in the part of the exam related to the content of the project and showed a higher pass rate in the course.

These results suggest that project-based learning not only improves academic performance, but also favors knowledge retention [22]. This finding aligns with Ausubel's [23] theory of meaningful learning, which emphasizes the importance of connecting new knowledge with the student's prior knowledge. Furthermore, it is related to Thomas' [24] proposal on the need to develop competencies valued in the professional field, such as problem solving, creativity and time management.

The development of an educational project that applies what the student learns theoretically fosters deep and meaningful learning. This allows students to apply what they have learned in real contexts, which is crucial for their professional development [17]. This study supports the use of active, practice-based methodologies in higher education, highlighting the importance of connecting theory with practice to enhance learning and prepare students for the professional world.

Future studies could explore the application of this approach in other disciplines and educational contexts to assess its effectiveness and adaptability. It would also be useful to consider students' feedback on their motivation toward the content and its applicability to professional practice. In addition, researching the long-term impact of this methodology on students' employability and professional development could provide a more complete picture of its benefits.

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